

IMPLEMENTATION OF MARKETING MIX STRATEGY IN ATTRACTING PATIENTS' INTEREST IN TREATMENT AT MAYJEN HM RYACUDU REGIONAL HOSPITAL, BUMI CITY, NORTH LAMPUNG REGENCY

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Abstract

The decline in outpatient visits is a major challenge for regional hospitals amidst increasing competition in healthcare services. This study aims to analyze the implementation of the 7P marketing mix (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, and Physical Evidence) in increasing outpatient visits at Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital in Kotabumi, Lampung. The study used a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with management, medical personnel, and patients, which were then validated through source triangulation, field observation, and documentation. Then, they were analyzed using data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion drawing techniques. The results show that price and place elements are the hospital's main strengths due to affordable rates and strategic location. However, limited pricing flexibility due to government regulations limits the function of price as a differentiation tool. People and process elements play a significant role in shaping patient perceptions of service quality, while promotion has not been optimally utilized. A SWOT analysis places the hospital in a position that requires aggressive market penetration through service digitalization and physical facility modernization to restore public trust and increase visits by BPJS and general patients. This study emphasizes the importance of integrating all elements of the 7P marketing mix synergistically to increase patient interest in visiting regional hospitals.

Keywords: *Marketing Mix 7P; Patient Visit Interest; Regional Hospital; Interest in Treatment*

INTRODUCTION

The paradigm shift of hospitals from purely social institutions to competitive entities demands adaptive marketing strategies. Competition in the Indonesian healthcare industry is intensifying along with the growth of private hospitals and rising public expectations for service quality. Regional hospitals face structural challenges in the form of limited regulations and resources, which impact the competitiveness of services. A serious challenge is the fluctuation of patient visits that have not reached targets in the past four years. This phenomenon indicates a disconnect between the identity of affordable government hospitals and the quality expectations of modern society. Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital in Kotabumi has experienced a decline in outpatient visits in recent years, necessitating an evaluation of healthcare marketing strategies based on the service marketing mix. Marketing in the healthcare sector is no longer simply a promotional tool, but rather a managerial function that creates value for patients. The use of the 7Ps framework (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, and Physical Evidence) is relevant for analyzing the complexity of medical services. Unlike previous research that focused primarily on the private sector, this study focuses on the challenges faced by regional hospitals, which face fiscal constraints but possess significant market potential through the BPJS (Social Security) system.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. The research location is Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital, Kotabumi, North Lampung. Research informants include hospital management, medical personnel, administrative staff, and outpatients. Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews, direct observation of the service flow, and analysis of supporting documents. Data analysis was conducted

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interactively through the stages of data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions with data validity testing using triangulation of sources, techniques, and time.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital is located at Jl. Jenderal Sudirman No. 2, Kotabumi, established in 1970 by the New Order Government in Kota Bumi, North Lampung Regency. This hospital is a local government-owned hospital with type C and Public Service Agency (BLU) status which functions as the main health referral center in the region with services and various facilities for the people of North Lampung and surrounding districts. The presentation of this data aims to describe the empirical conditions of the implementation of the 7P strategy, factors inhibiting patient interest in treatment, and the potential role of the marketing mix in increasing visits. As seen in the picture below:

Based on the results of the research conducted by the author, the findings of this study strengthen the theory of the service marketing mix which emphasizes the importance of integration between the 7P elements. In the context of regional hospitals, regulatory limitations require innovation in non-price elements such as people, processes, and promotions to increase patient interest in visits.

1. Overview of the 7P Elements (Product, Price, Place, Promotion, People, Process, and Physical Evidence) at the Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital

a. Product

A gap was found between the availability of poly and the perception of value.

"We have 14 polyclinics for each type of service, but there are none that are superior, sis" (Management Informant, 2025).

This leads patients to feel there is no specific reason to choose the regional general hospital other than compulsion (referral). Healthcare services provided by the Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital include both basic and specialist medical services. Field findings indicate that patients consider the quality of medical services to be quite good, but the limited availability of certain supporting facilities impacts perceptions of quality. In service marketing theory, the quality of a service product is perceived through direct consumer experience (Kotler & Keller, 2020). Recent studies have shown that consistent service quality is a crucial factor in increasing patient visit intention.

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The hospital currently operates at a standard level of service without significant differentiation. The lack of superior services has led patients to perceive the regional hospital as merely a place for routine procedures, even though the planned CT scan is projected to be a game-changer in the North Lampung region.

b. Price

It is a major attraction factor but is rigid due to its dependence on regulations.

"There are no subsidies or discounts, because on average, BPJS patients follow the BPJS tariff pattern" (All Informants, 2025).

Regional public hospitals (RSUD) charge 70-80% less than their private competitors, but have not significantly converted general patients. RSUD service rates are relatively lower than those of private hospitals in North Lampung. While a major draw, low prices do not automatically increase non-BPJS patients due to limited flexibility imposed by regulations. Recent research shows that non-price strategies are more effective in increasing patient visits in regional hospitals.

c. Place

The strategic location of the regional hospital in the city center facilitates patient access. This finding aligns with the service accessibility theory, which states that location convenience influences consumer decisions in selecting healthcare services. The place element was deemed to significantly support patient visit interest due to the hospital's strategic location and easy access. This finding aligns with the service location theory, which states that accessibility influences consumer decisions (Kotler & Keller, 2020).

d. Promotion

Promotional activities at regional hospitals (RSUD) are still limited and not yet strategically integrated. The minimal use of digital media results in inadequate service delivery to the public. Recent studies emphasize the importance of health education-based promotions and digital media in increasing patient interest; some communication strategies remain reactive. The PKRS unit has not yet optimally utilized social media to stem negative public opinion. Promotions are not being utilized optimally due to the lack of a planned and integrated marketing communication strategy, so the potential for service excellence is not widely communicated to the public. Promotional activities are still conventional and sporadic. Minimal penetration through social media platforms such as Instagram and TikTok hinders the formation of a positive image in the eyes of the younger generation and the digital community.

e. People

Medical personnel competence and service attitude are crucial factors in building patient trust. However, workload and limited human resources impact service consistency. This aligns with recent research that places people as the dominant element in regional hospital services. The loyalty of specialist doctors is crucial social capital, but a lack of systematic training for administrative and nursing staff often impacts perceptions of service friendliness.

f. Process

The service process was deemed quite clear, but challenges remained with waiting times and inter-unit coordination. Process efficiency is a key determinant of patient satisfaction and interest in visits. The implementation of online registration via WhatsApp is underway, but physical queues remain, indicating a suboptimal integration of digital systems with on-site workflows.

g. Physical Evidence

Its weakest point is its aging building, complaints about poor sanitation facilities, and the use of plastic chairs that don't meet professional hospital standards. This has led to patients switching to private hospitals that offer a more comfortable environment. This is the variable that is most frequently complained about and triggers patient switching behavior.

"I don't want to go back unless the health center tells me to, the toilet smells unbearable, the in-patient bed is full of holes..." (Patient Informant, 2025).

The decrepit condition of the building (low ratings) negates the positive effect of the doctor's competence, which is generally perceived as friendly by patients. However, in some cases, physical evidence such as cleanliness,

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comfortable waiting rooms, and supporting facilities contribute to perceptions of service quality. Recent studies have shown that a comfortable physical environment increases patient trust and engagement.

2. Strategy to Increase Interest in Medical Treatment

The SWOT analysis results place the regional general hospital (RSUD) in a competitive position if it can capitalize on its pricing and location strengths to offset infrastructure weaknesses. The urgent need to renovate physical facilities and improve digital literacy through health education content is a priority to change negative public perceptions. Consistent with the findings of Pitaloka & Harianto (2025), the comfort of physical facilities is a key determinant of patient satisfaction, surpassing price considerations. Based on the results of the identification of internal (IFAS) and external (EFAS) variables processed from observations and documentation, the following is a strategy matrix for optimizing interest in seeking treatment:

<p>IFAS</p>	<p>Strengths (S)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Price</i>competitive according to Regional Regulation No. 3/2011 (3-5x cheaper) 2. <i>Place</i>strategic location in the city center + spacious parking 3. <i>Process</i>fast WA online hybrid registration 4. <i>People</i>high loyalty specialist doctor 	<p>Weaknesses (W)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Physical Evidence</i>old building/plastic chairs 2. <i>Promotion</i>minimal low frequency IG/WA 3. <i>Product</i>without superior service 4. <i>People</i>staff without systemic training
<p>EFAS</p> <p>Opportunities (O)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. BPJS expands JKN coverage in 2026 2. Digitizing IG Live/Linktree engagement 3. Ministry of Health's Physical DAK for renovations Rp. 25 billion 4. North Lampung's first CT Scan 	<p>SO Strategy</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Take advantageSuperiority Price and Process hybrid online for weekly IG Live with specialist doctors 2. Cheap Premium CT Scan at the Launch of LTU's first CT Scan service with Regional Regulation rates together with specialist doctors 3. Create an event with the local government by utilizing a strategic location with on-site WA registration and Live IG 	<p>WO Strategy</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Prioritize standard chairs for patients and air conditioning from the 2026 DAK budget plan of IDR 25 billion 2. OrganizingFree Digital Training in Collaboration with the LTU Health Office for customer service training via Zoom 3. Optimizationuse of social media by uploading 3x Stories/registration day and weekly doctor's IG Live

Strategic Position: The calculation results show a value of X = 0.85 and Y = 0.23, which places RSUD Mayjen HM Ryacudu in Quadrant I (Aggressive). This means the hospital has sufficient internal strength to maximize external opportunities.

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Quadrant I allows Ryacudu Regional General Hospital to implement an aggressive growth-oriented SO (Strengths-Opportunities) strategy, including maximizing the leverage of Regional Regulation tariffs for BPJS expansion, developing regional differentiation through CT Scans in strategic locations, accelerating digital market penetration via WA/IG, and improving service excellence with DAK renovations and specialist doctors. The strategic implications of Quadrant I position place Ryacudu Regional General Hospital as a potential market leader in North Lampung, having the potential for BPJS patients to become a dominant market share through a combination of physical renovations and integrated digital transformation.

CONCLUSION

The 7P marketing mix plays a crucial role in increasing outpatient visits at Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital. While affordability and strategic location are key strengths, optimizing non-price elements such as people, processes, and promotions is crucial for sustainably improving the competitiveness of regional hospitals. The study found that price is the primary attraction of Mayjen HM Ryacudu Regional General Hospital, as service rates are 70–80% lower than those of private hospitals in North Lampung. However, reliance on regional regulations and the Social Security Agency (BPJS) prevents the hospital from having flexibility in pricing innovation, preventing it from being used as a strategic differentiation tool.

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